

CHEMORHEOLOGY AND CURE KINETICS OF A CARBON NANOTUBE FILLED EPOXY SYSTEM

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SUMMARY

This work presents an experimental study to characterize the cure kinetics and chemorheology of a carbon nanotube filled epoxy resin system. The experimental measurements are presented as generalized correlations as functions of the carbon nanotube parameters.

Keywords: carbon nanotubes, chemorheology, cure kinetics, epoxy, viscosity

INTRODUCTION

Nanocomposites based on thermosetting resin matrix reinforced with nanofillers such as nanoclays or carbon nanotubes have been studied quite extensively in recent years, for their promise of significantly improved properties. Specifically, nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes have been reported to reduce thermal expansion coefficient [1] while increasing thermal and electrical conductivities [1,2] modulus [2,3], durability [2,4] and strength [2–4], while nanocomposites filled with nanoclays have been shown to improve toughness [5], increase the heat distortion temperature [6,7] and reduce the apparent activation energy of the cure reaction [8].

Many of the studies reported in the literature have focused on quantifying the properties of the nanocomposites as a function of the nanofiller morphology and loading. Ajayan, et al., [3,4] studied the use of single-walled and multi-walled carbon nanotubes as reinforcement in an epoxy matrix using Raman spectroscopy to measure the strain held by a carbon nanotube under load. Xu, et al., [1] measured the effects of single-walled carbon nanotubes on the thermal properties of a thermoplastic composite and found reductions in the coefficient of thermal expansion and increased thermal conductivity due to carbon nanotubes. Kim et al., [9] studied the effects of oxidation of multi-walled carbon nanotubes on the electrical conductivity of a carbon nanotube-epoxy composite and found increased conductivity of the nanocomposite as long as no damage to the multi-walled carbon nanotubes occurred during oxidation. A large volume of literature also exists on studying the properties of nanocomposites reinforced with nanoclays [10].

Although several studies have focused on the properties of nanocomposites, fabrication of nanocomposites has been less systematically investigated [10]. Fundamentally, design of the fabrication processes will require information on the viscosity and cure kinetics of thermosetting resin systems with nanofillers [8]. The objective of the present

Table 1: Ranges of Carbon Nanotube Parameters Considered in the Study

Sample No.	CN Type	Diameter [nm]	Length [μm]	CN wt. %	Aspect Ratio Range
1	–	–	–	0.0	–
2	MWCN	30 \pm 15	1–5	0.1	22–333
3				0.3	
4				0.5	
5	MWCN	15 \pm 5	1–5	0.1	50–500
6				0.3	
7				0.5	
8	MWCN	30 \pm 15	5–20	0.1	111–1333
9				0.3	
10				0.5	
11	MWCN	15 \pm 5	5–20	0.1	250–2000
12				0.3	
13				0.5	
14	SWCN	< 2	no spec.	0.1	–
15				0.3	
16				0.5	
17	pSWCN	< 2	0.5–120	0.1	250–60,000
18				0.3	
19				0.5	

study is to systematically characterize the viscosity and cure kinetics of a carbon nanotube filled catalyzed epoxy resin system, toward establishing the fundamental information needed for processing of nanocomposites based on these materials.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

A systematic experimental study was performed to determine the cure kinetics and viscosity of EPON 815C resin catalyzed with EPICURE 3274 curing agent and containing varying amounts, morphologies, and aspect ratios of carbon nanotube fillers. Carbon nanotubes of three types were investigated: multi-walled, research grade ($> 95\%$ purity), carbon nanotubes (MWCN) supplied by NanoLab (Newton, MA), and single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCN) and purified single-walled carbon nanotubes (pSWCN), both supplied by SES Research (Houston, TX). For each type, different combinations of diameters, lengths, and weight percentages were considered. Table 1 enumerates the various combinations resulting in 18 carbon-nanotube-filled resin-catalyst samples and one sample with no carbon nanotubes, for a total of 19 samples. As seen in Table 1, the MWCN diameters were nominally 15 ± 5 nm or 30 ± 15 nm and their nominal lengths were either 1–5 μm or 5–20 μm . The SWCN used in the study were produced using the arc process and had a purity of 20–40% (other materials included metal catalyst and amorphous carbon and carbon nanoparticles); their nominal diameter was ranged from 1.2–1.4 nm and their nominal length was in the range of 2–5 μm . The pSWCN fillers were treated to open their ends, and had a purity of up to 75%. Table 1

also lists the range of aspect ratios based on the nominal length and diameter values, for reference in the analysis of the results of the experiments. For each combination of carbon nanotube morphology, length, and diameter, three weight percentages of 0.1%, 0.3%, and 0.5% were considered. The sample preparation and experimental characterization are described in the following subsections.

Sample Preparation

Samples for both cure kinetics and viscosity experiments were prepared by a process of weighing, hand mixing, ultrasonic processing, and degassing. First, appropriate amounts of carbon nanotubes and EPON 815C resin were weighed using an Ohaus Explorer Pro precision balance (Ohaus Corporation, Pine Brook, NJ) and hand mixed in a sample vial. Next, the carbon nanotubes were dispersed in the resin using a Cole-Parmer 500 watt ultrasonic processor with a 1/4 in tapered microtip. The microtip of the ultrasonic processor, driven by a piezoelectric device, oscillated at 20 kHz and generated pressure waves that deagglomerated carbon nanotube clusters held together by van der Waals forces thereby promoting uniform dispersion. The sample vial was partially submerged in water bath to maintain a low temperature during processing and to avoid heat build-up that could degrade the resin. The end of the tapered microtip was submerged in the sample, taking care to ensure that the tip did not contact the sample vial and each sample was sonified for 2 hours at the minimum amplitude setting of 20% in a pulsed mode with the input being alternated on and off for one second duration each. Sonification in the pulsed mode further reduced the energy input rate to the sample to allow time for heat to dissipate to the water bath, and ensured that the sample temperature never exceeded 50 °C during processing. Finally, the sample was degassed in a vacuum chamber at 25 in. Hg for 30 minutes. Immediately prior to each individual experiment resin (with dispersed carbon nanotubes) and curing agent were measured using syringes with 10 μ L divisions and thoroughly hand mixed at a 2.19:1 ratio (by volume) to make approximately 2 mL of total sample. These prepared samples were utilized in the cure kinetics and viscosity experiments as outlined below.

Cure Kinetics Characterization

The cure kinetics of the catalyzed epoxy resin with and without carbon nanotubes were characterized using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) (Model: DSC 2920 from TA Instruments, New Castle, DE). For each experiment, a small amount of the epoxy-curing agent-carbon nanotube mixture was placed in a sample pan, crimp-sealed, and weighed. The samples were tested under a dynamic (nonisothermal) condition as well as several isothermal conditions. In the dynamic measurements, the sample was placed in the DSC chamber, and the temperature was ramped at a rate of 10 °C/min from room temperature to 225 °C, where the reaction was seen to be complete. The exothermic heat flow rate during the experiment was measured as a function of time, and the area under the heat flow curve represents the heat of the reaction, ΔH_R .

Isothermal measurements of heat flow were performed on the 19 different samples at four different target temperatures of 80 °C, 90 °C, 100 °C, and 110 °C to determine the temperature-dependent reaction rate. The isothermal heat flow measurements were

converted to cure rate ($d\varepsilon/dt$) values by dividing the heat flow rate, \dot{Q} , by the heat of the reaction, ΔH_R . Integrating the time-dependent cure rate plot from the initial time ($t = 0$) to any time, t , yields the degree of cure, $\varepsilon(t)$.

The plots of cure rate variation with the degree of cure were expressed in terms of an empirical correlation of the form below, which has been used to describe the cure kinetics of the EPON 815C/EPICURE 3274 system in a previous study [11]:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = K \cdot \varepsilon^m (1 - \varepsilon)^n; \quad \text{where } K = K_o \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

For each temperature, the values of K , m , and n were determined through a nonlinear regression of the data on cure rate as a function of the degree of cure. As is commonly observed for autocatalytic reactions [11–14], the values of m and n were determined to be such that $m + n = 2$. From the values of K for the four different temperatures, the frequency factor, K_o , and the activation energy for the cure reaction, E , were obtained from a semi-log plot of K with respect to the inverse of the absolute temperature (in Kelvin); the slope of a linear regression fit through the data represents $-E/R$ and the intercept on the vertical axis denotes $\ln(K_o)$.

The kinetics parameters, K_o , E , m and n were determined for all the samples listed in Table 1 following the methodology presented above. The effect of the carbon nanotube parameters on the cure kinetics is discussed in the section on presentation of results.

Viscosity Characterization

Viscosity of the 19 samples in Table 1 was measured dynamically throughout the cure process using a Brookfield CAP 2000+ cone-and-plate viscometer (Brookfield Engineering, Middleboro, MA) with the goal of characterizing the viscosity as a function of degree of cure, temperature, shear rate, carbon nanotube filler content, morphology, and carbon nanotube aspect ratio. The epoxy-carbon-nanotube sample prepared following the steps described earlier in this section was hand-mixed with the curing agent, and a drop of the mixture was immediately placed on the preheated viscometer plate. Four isothermal temperatures of 30, 45, 60 and 75 °C were considered in the experiments. The shear rate for the experiment was set by adjusting the rotational speed of the cone.

An empirical correlation for viscosity as a function of temperature and degree of cure suggested for epoxy resin systems in the literature [15] is modified here to include additionally the power law dependence on shear rate, and is expressed as follows:

$$\eta = M \cdot \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}; \quad \text{where } M = A \exp\left(\frac{E_n}{RT} + B\varepsilon\right) \quad (2)$$

Here, η is the viscosity of the resin system, T is the temperature in Kelvin, ε is the degree of cure, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate, E_η is the activation energy, and R is the universal gas constant. The term denoted as M represents the consistency index as a function of temperature and degree of cure, in which A and B are empirical constants. The term n_I represents the power law exponent, which is expected to be less than unity based on the shear-thinning characteristic observed in the experiments.

The values of A , B , E_η , and n_I completely characterize the viscosity as a function of cure and temperature of the resin system with carbon nanotube fillers. The effects of the carbon nanotubes on the viscosity are discussed in the following section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cure kinetics and viscosity of the resin systems filled with carbon nanotubes are characterized by their respective sets of parameters: ΔH_R , K_o , E , m and n ; and A , B , E_η , and n_I . The variation of these parameters with carbon nanotube loading, morphology, and aspect ratio is examined in this section.

The differential scanning calorimetric measurements on the 19 samples resulted in the heat of the reaction values, ΔH_R , from about 315–360 J/g, with no distinct trend with respect to the carbon nanotube loading, aspect ratio, or morphology. This suggests that the carbon nanotubes do not affect the exothermic heat release from the reaction, and an average value of 349.6 J/g from the 19 experiments is taken to be the heat of the reaction for the samples. Similarly, the presence of the carbon nanotubes was found to have minimal effect on the shape parameters, m and n , which were taken to be the values corresponding to the neat resin sample (Sample 1 in Table 1): $m = 0.207$ and $n = 1.793$.

The effects of the carbon nanotube loading on the reaction kinetics is represented by a modification to the cure kinetics model (Eq. 1) to introduce the carbon nanotube loading dependence of the activation energy as follows:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = K \cdot \varepsilon^m (1 - \varepsilon)^n; \quad \text{where } K = K_o \exp\left(\frac{-E(1 - \omega)^{2.5}}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

The frequency factor and the activation energy of a neat resin/catalyst sample without any added carbon nanotubes (Sample 1 in Table 1), K_o and E in Eq. (5) which were determined to be 6.83×10^6 1/s and -64.672 kJ/mol. In Eq. 3 ω represents the carbon nanotube loading expressed as a weight fraction. It is noted from the modified cure kinetics relationship above that the effect of the carbon nanotube loading is to decrease the activation energy relative to those for the unfilled resin/catalyst system. This result is also consistent with the decrease in the activation energy reported for nanoclay filled systems in ref. [8]. Furthermore it is seen that for $\omega = 0$, the generalized equation for an unfilled kinetics (Eq. 1) defaults to the resin-catalyst system.

Figure 1 compares the prediction of the rate constant, K , using the correlation above with the individually measured rate constants for all the samples studied. The solid line

Figure 1: Comparison of the rate constants predicted by the generalized cure kinetics equation (Eq. 3) with those measured on the individual samples, for all the 19 samples listed in Table 1.

diagonal to the plot frame is the line of exact agreement and the dashed lines denote the 15% error bands. It is seen that the predictions of the rate constant are accurate to within 15% in almost all cases.

The power law exponent, n_1 , and the consistency index, M , including its constituent parameters, A , B , and E_η , in Eq. 2 were determined for all the 19 samples listed in Table 1 following the procedure outlined in the preceding section. Based on the results for the various Samples with different carbon nanotube parameters, the power law exponent, n_1 , was found to decrease with increasing concentration of the carbon nanotubes suggesting an increased shear-thinning behavior with increasing carbon nanotube content, as is commonly expected for particulate filled systems [16]. However, no distinct trend was observed with either the aspect ratio or the morphology of the nanotubes. The exponent was found to correlate well with the carbon nanotube weight fraction, ω , as $n_1 = 1 + 30.3 \log_{10}(1 - \omega)$, where the constant (30.3) was determined through a least-squares fit of exponent values with ω . Note that the form of the correlation is consistent with that used to represent the shear-thinning behavior with particulate volume fraction in ceramic slurries, reported in [16], and is such that the Newtonian behavior of unfilled catalyzed resin system is recovered for $\omega = 0$.

Figure 2: Validation of the generalized viscosity model (Eq. 4) with the measured viscosity data, for all the 19 samples listed in Table 1.

The consistency index values of the 19 samples indicated an increase with the carbon nanotube weight fraction, ω , for a given degree of cure, ε , and temperature, T . In order to characterize the weight-fraction-dependence, the variation of M with the weight fraction was represented as $M = \eta_o \cdot f(\omega)$, where η_o is the viscosity of the unfilled resin-catalyst system (Sample 1 in Table 1), $\eta_o = A \exp\left(\frac{E_\eta}{RT} + B\varepsilon\right)$, and $f(\omega)$ is the dependence of the consistency index on the weight fraction of the carbon nanotubes, such that Eq. 2 can be expressed as: $M = \eta_o \cdot f(\omega) \cdot \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$. The function $f(\omega)$ was expressed as $\exp(K_\eta \omega / (1 - \omega))$, which mimics the form of the Mooney equation commonly used to model the rheology of particulate suspensions [17] with the modification that the carbon nanotube weight fraction, a more easily measurable quantity for carbon nanotubes, is used here instead of the particulate volume fraction in the Mooney equation.

Based on the foregoing representation of the dependence of the consistency index and the power law exponent on the carbon nanotube parameters, the viscosity is expressed

in a generalized form as:

$$\eta = A \exp\left(\frac{E_\eta}{RT} + B\varepsilon + \frac{K_\eta \omega}{(1-\omega)}\right) \cdot \dot{\gamma}^{30.3 \log_{10}(1-\omega)} \quad (4)$$

in which: $A = 6.16 \times 10^{-11}$ Pa.s; $B = 3.76$; $E_\eta = 55.947$ kJ/mol; $K_\eta = 170$ (MWCN) or 148 (SWCN and pSWCN). The coefficient, K_η , being different for the MWCN and the SWCN/pSWCN samples suggests the aspect ratio dependence of the viscosity. Since the aspect ratio values were not reliably known, no attempt was made to establish a quantitative relationship with the aspect ratio. Table 1 shows that the single-walled carbon nanotubes nominally had a higher aspect ratio range relative to the multi-walled carbon nanotubes. The lower K_η value for SWCN/pSWCN points to a better alignment of the larger aspect ratio single-walled carbon nanotubes in the shear flow leading to a lower viscosity, although further studies are warranted for a conclusive determination.

The overall accuracy of the general viscosity equation (Eq. 4) for all the samples and measurement conditions considered in this study is summarized in Fig. 2 where the predicted viscosity using Eq. 7 is plotted against the experimentally measured viscosity for degree of cure values less than 0.4. The solid diagonal line is the line of exact agreement and the dashed lines represent the $\pm 15\%$ error bands. Figure 2 represents over 25,000 measured viscosity data points, of which more than 90% fall within the 15% error bands. The generalized viscosity equation given Eq. 7, therefore, represents a reliable viscosity model for evaluating the viscosity of the carbon nanotube filled epoxy resin system considered here. The generalized viscosity model given by Eq. 7 is demonstrated to be valid over the range of measurements considered in this study namely, temperatures between 25–75 °C; $\varepsilon < 0.4$ (which represents pre-gelation conditions of the resin-catalyst system); and shear rate in the range 1,333–10,666 s⁻¹.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study was conducted to determine the cure kinetics and viscosity characteristics of EPON 815C/EPICURE 3274 resin-catalyst system with carbon nanotube fillers, over a range of carbon nanotube loading, morphologies, and aspect ratios. The study revealed that the heat of the cure reaction as well as the shape parameters of the cure kinetics expression were unaffected by the presence of the carbon nanotubes, whereas the activation energy was decreased with the addition of carbon nanotubes. Viscosity measurements indicated that the addition of carbon nanotubes to resin systems increases the viscosity, and introduces a distinct shear-thinning rheology, with the shear thinning effect increasing with increasing carbon nanotube content. Generalized models for the cure kinetics and the viscosity of the carbon nanotube filled resin system were presented and validated.

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